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Tolerance profiles of the ILC lineage.

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ILC1 cells were distinguished by LAG3 expression, but did not express AHR. The ILC3 signature was defined by TOX and TOX2 expression, and distinguished from ILC3 by AHR expression. Exhaustion and tolerance pathway factors and surface receptors were defining components of the ILC lineage gene signature.

Citations

1. Lyu, M., Suzuki, H., Kang, L., Gaspal, F., Zhou, W., Goc, J., Zhou, L., Zhou, J., Zhang, W. and Shen, Z., 2022. ILC3s select microbiota-specific regulatory T cells to establish tolerance in the gut. Nature, 610(7933), pp.744-751.